

Appendix A: Relating k_L to α :

The compartment model analyzed in this work is described by the matrix equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I \\ S \\ A \\ C \end{bmatrix}' = \begin{bmatrix} -k_D & 0 & \alpha k_R & \alpha k_R \\ k_B & k_B - k_D - k_I \frac{A}{A+S+I} & k_B + (1-\alpha)k_R & k_B + (1-\alpha)k_R \\ 0 & k_I \frac{A}{A+S+I} & -(k_R + k_D + k_P) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_P & -(k_R + k_D + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I \\ S \\ A \\ C \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

which is equivalent to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I \\ S \\ A \\ C \end{bmatrix}' = \begin{bmatrix} -k_D - k_L & 0 & k_R & k_R \\ k_B + k_L & k_B - k_D - k_I \frac{A}{A+S+I} & k_B & k_B \\ 0 & k_I \frac{A}{A+S+I} & -(k_R + k_D + k_P) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_P & -(k_R + k_D + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I \\ S \\ A \\ C \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $k_L = (1-\alpha)k_R(A+C)/I$. While the dynamics of these two systems are very different, this expression may be used to solve for k_L at endemic equilibrium for any α .

Appendix B: derivation of R_0 :

The linearized infection subsystem, in the limit of a completely susceptible population, is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A \\ C \end{bmatrix}' = \begin{bmatrix} k_I - (k_R + k_D + k_P) & \beta k_I \\ k_P & -(k_R + k_D + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A \\ C \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The rates, R , may be written as the sum of two matrices: T , transmission events leading to new infections and E , all other events:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} k_I & \beta k_I \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, E = \begin{bmatrix} -(k_R + k_D + k_P) & 0 \\ k_P & -(k_R + k_D + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The next generation matrix, NGM , may then be computed as the, sign corrected, product:

$$NGM = -TE^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{k_I}{k_R + k_D + k_P} + \frac{\beta k_I k_P}{(k_R + k_D + k_P)(k_R + k_D + k_{DV})} & \frac{\beta k_I}{k_R + k_D + k_{DV}} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

with the characteristic equation:

$$-\lambda \left(\frac{k_I}{k_R + k_D + k_P} + \frac{\beta k_I k_P}{(k_R + k_D + k_P)(k_R + k_D + k_{DV})} - \lambda \right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where R_0 is the dominant, in this case nonzero, eigenvalue.

Appendix C: solution for endemic equilibrium with constant population:

At endemic equilibrium the fraction of the total population, N , in each compartment, X , is constant: $(\frac{X}{N})' = x' - xn' = x' = 0$ when the population is constant:

$$0 = \begin{bmatrix} i \\ s \\ a \\ c \end{bmatrix}' = \begin{bmatrix} -k_D & 0 & \alpha k_R & \alpha k_R \\ k_B & k_B - k_D - k_I \frac{a^* + \beta c^*}{i^* + s^* + a^* + \beta c^*} & k_B + (1-\alpha)k_R & k_B + (1-\alpha)k_R \\ 0 & k_I \frac{a^* + \beta c^*}{i^* + s^* + a^* + \beta c^*} & -(k_R + k_D + k_P) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_P & -(k_R + k_D + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i^* \\ s^* \\ a^* \\ c^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

which asserts the additional constraint $k_B = k_D + k_{DV}c^*$. The epressions for a^* , i^* , and s^* may be rewritten in terms of c^* . Subsequently enforcing unity, $i^* + s^* + a^* + c^* = 1$ yields a unique solution:

$$c^* = \left[\alpha k_2 + \frac{k_3(\alpha k_2 + k_1 + \beta)}{\left(1 + \frac{\beta}{k_1}\right) - k_3} + k_1 + 1 \right]^{-1} = \left[\frac{R_0 - 1}{(\alpha k_2 + k_1 + 1)R_0 - (1 - \beta)} \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$k_1 = \frac{k_R + k_D + k_{DV}}{k_P}, k_2 = \frac{k_R}{k_D}(1 + k_1), k_3 = \frac{k_R + k_D + k_P}{k_I} \quad (9)$$

As noted in the main text, this critical point does not correspond to a stable endemic equilibrium for all parameter regimes. For regimes where endemic equilibrium does exist, the derivative with respect to α/β can inform the impact of immunity and isolation of symptomatic hosts respectively:

$$\frac{\partial c^*}{\partial \alpha} = - (c^*)^{-2} \frac{k_R}{k_D} \left(1 + \frac{k_R + k_D + k_{DV}}{k_P} \right) \left[1 + \frac{1}{R_0 - 1} \right] \quad (10)$$

and

$$-\frac{\partial c^*}{\partial \beta} = - (c^*)^{-2} \left[\frac{1}{(R_0 - 1)^2} \left(1 + \alpha \frac{k_2}{k_1 k_3} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

One may additionally compare the limiting cases:

$$\frac{c^*(\alpha = 0)}{c^*(\alpha = 1)} = 1 + \frac{k_R}{k_D} \frac{R_0}{R_0 + \left(\frac{k_1 + \beta}{k_1 + 1} - 1 \right)} \geq 1 + \frac{k_R}{k_D} \quad (12)$$

which yields a decreasing function of β and

$$\frac{c^*(\beta = 1)}{c^*(\beta = 0)} = 1 + \frac{k_3}{1 + \frac{1}{k_1}} \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{k_1} \right) - k_3}{1 - k_3} \frac{(\alpha k_2 + k_1)}{(\alpha k_2 + k_1 + 1)} - 1 \right) \geq 1 + \frac{k_1}{1 - k_3} \left(\frac{k_3}{1 + k_1} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

which yields an increasing function of α . Immunity and isolation work in concert.

Appendix D: general solution for endemic equilibrium:

All rates are normalized by the rate of infection.

$$0 = \sum_{i=0}^4 \left(\sum_j \lambda_{ij} k_{DV}^j \right) c^{*i} \quad (14)$$

where:

$$\lambda_{43} = (1 - \beta) k_P - 1 \quad (15)$$

$$\lambda_{33} = 2 - (2 - \beta) k_P \quad (16)$$

$$\lambda_{33} = \alpha k_R + \beta (k_P + 3k_B k_P + 2k_P k_R + k_P^2) + 3k_B + k_P + 2k_R - 3k_B k_P - 2k_P k_R - k_P^2 \quad (17)$$

$$\lambda_{23} = -2\alpha k_R + \beta (-k_P - 2k_B k_P - k_P k_R - k_P^2) + 5k_B k_P - 2k_P - 2k_R - 4k_B + 3k_P k_R + 2k_P^2 \quad (18)$$

$$\lambda_{21} = -\alpha \beta k_P k_R + \alpha (-2k_B k_R - k_P k_R - 2k_R^2) + \quad (19)$$

$$\beta (-3k_B^2 k_P - 2k_B k_P^2 - 4k_B k_P k_R - 2k_B k_P - k_P^2 k_R - k_P^2 - k_P k_R^2 - k_P k_R) +$$

$$3k_B^2 k_P - 3k_B^2 + 2k_B k_P^2 + 4k_B k_P k_R - 2k_B k_P - 4k_B k_R + k_P^2 k_R + k_P k_R^2 - k_P k_R - k_R^2$$

$$\lambda_{12} = \alpha k_R + k_B + k_P - 2k_B k_P - k_P k_R - k_P^2 \quad (20)$$

$$\lambda_{11} = \alpha \beta k_P k_R + \alpha (2k_B k_R + k_P k_R + 2k_R^2) + \beta (k_B k_P + k_B k_P^2 + k_B^2 k_P + k_P^2 + k_B k_P k_R) + \quad (21)$$

$$2k_B^2 - 4k_B^2 k_P - 3k_B k_P^2 - 5k_B k_P k_R + 3k_B k_P + 2k_B k_R - k_P^2 k_R - k_P k_R^2 + k_P k_R$$

$$\lambda_{10} = \alpha\beta k_P k_R (k_B + k_P + k_R) + \alpha (k_R^2 + k_B * k_R) (k_B + k_P + k_R) + \quad (22)$$

$$\beta (k_B + k_P + k_R) (k_B k_P + k_B^2 k_P + k_B k_P k_R) + (k_B + k_P + k_R) (k_B k_R - k_B^2 k_P + k_B^2 - k_B k_P k_R)$$

$$\lambda_{01} = k_B k_P (k_B + k_P + k_R - 1) \quad (23)$$

$$\lambda_{00} = -\beta k_B k_P^2 + k_B k_P (k_B k_P - k_R - k_B + 2k_B k_R + k_P k_R + k_B^2 + k_R^2) \quad (24)$$

Appendix E: solution for endemic equilibrium in the limit of $c^* \ll 1$ and $k_P > k_R + k_{DV}$:
This limit yields the simplified system:

$$0 = \begin{bmatrix} I/N \\ S/N \\ A/N \\ C/N \end{bmatrix}' \approx \begin{bmatrix} c^* k_{DV} - k_B & 0 & \alpha k_R & \alpha k_R \\ k_B & c^* k_{DV} - k_I (a^* + \beta c^*) & k_B + (1 - \alpha) k_R & k_B + (1 - \alpha) k_R \\ 0 & k_I (a^* + \beta c^*) & c^* k_{DV} - (k_R + k_P) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_P & -(k_R + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i^* \\ s^* \\ a^* \\ c^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

First a note about R_0 . In this case the linearized infection subsystem, in the limit of a completely susceptible population, becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A/N \\ C/N \end{bmatrix}' \approx \begin{bmatrix} k_I - (k_R + k_P) + C k_{DV} & \beta k_I \\ k_P & -(k_R + k_{DV}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A/N \\ C/N \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

We note this system is approximately the same as that introduced in Appendix A given $1 \gg \frac{k_B, k_D}{k_R}$ and $1 \gg c \frac{k_{DV}}{k_R}$ but may differ in general. The expressions for a^* and i^* may be rewritten in terms of c^* while:

$$s^* \approx \frac{k_R + k_P}{k_I \left(1 + \frac{\beta}{\frac{k_R + k_{DV}}{k_P}}\right)} \approx \frac{1}{R_0} \quad (27)$$

yielding:

$$c^* \approx \frac{k_B}{k_{DV}} \left(1 + \alpha \frac{k_R \left(\frac{k_R + k_{DV}}{k_P} + 1\right)}{k_{DV} \left(1 - \frac{1}{R_0}\right)}\right)^{-1} \quad (28)$$

which represents a stable endemic equilibrium for sufficiently large alpha (at least partial immunity). The derivative with respect to β can additionally inform the impact of isolation of symptomatic hosts:

$$-\frac{\partial c^*}{\partial \beta} \approx -\alpha \frac{k_I}{k_B} \frac{k_R + k_{DV} + k_P}{k_R + k_P} \frac{k_R}{k_R + k_{DV}} \left(\frac{c^*}{R_0 - 1}\right)^2 < -\alpha \frac{k_I}{k_B} \frac{k_R}{k_R + k_{DV}} \left(\frac{c^*}{R_0 - 1}\right)^2 \quad (29)$$

Appendix F: solution for endemic equilibrium in the limit of $1 \gg \frac{k_{DV}}{k_R}$:
This limit yields the simplified system:

$$0 = \begin{bmatrix} I/N \\ S/N \\ A/N \\ C/N \end{bmatrix}' \approx \begin{bmatrix} c^* k_{DV} - k_B & 0 & \alpha k_R & \alpha k_R \\ k_B & c^* k_{DV} - k_I \frac{a^* + \beta c^*}{i^* + s^* + a^* + \beta c^*} & k_B + (1 - \alpha) k_R & k_B + (1 - \alpha) k_R \\ 0 & k_I \frac{a^* + \beta c^*}{i^* + s^* + a^* + \beta c^*} & -(k_R + k_P) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_P & -k_R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i^* \\ s^* \\ a^* \\ c^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

The expressions for a^* , i^* , and s^* may be rewritten in terms of c^* yielding:

$$i^* + s^* + a^* + c^* \approx \frac{\alpha k_R \left(\frac{k_R}{k_P} + 1\right) c^*}{k_B - c^* k_{DV}} + \frac{1 - (1 - \beta) c^*}{R_0} + \left(\frac{k_R}{k_P} + 1\right) c^* = 1 \quad (31)$$

In the stricter limit $1 \gg c^* \frac{k_{DV}}{k_B}$, this yields:

$$c^* \approx \frac{R_0 - 1}{\left(\alpha \frac{k_R}{k_B} + 1\right) \left(\frac{k_R}{k_P} + 1\right) R_0 + \beta - 1} \quad (32)$$

Appendix G: stability analysis:

Let

$$\gamma \equiv (i + s + a + \beta c)^{-1} = (1 - (1 - \beta) c)^{-1} \quad (33)$$

and note

$$\frac{d}{dc} (a + \beta c) \gamma = \beta \gamma + (a + \beta c) (1 - \beta) \gamma^2 = (\beta + (1 - \beta) a) \gamma^2 \quad (34)$$

Let

$$f1 \equiv \frac{di}{dt}; f2 \equiv \frac{ds}{dt}; f3 \equiv \frac{da}{dt}; f4 \equiv \frac{dc}{dt} \quad (35)$$

This yields:

$$\frac{df1}{di} = ck_{DV} - k_B; \frac{df1}{ds} = 0; \frac{df1}{da} = \frac{df1}{dc} = \alpha k_R \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{df2}{di} = 0; \frac{df2}{ds} = -k_B + ck_{DV} - k_I (a + \beta c) \gamma; \frac{df2}{da} = -k_I s \gamma + (1 - \alpha) k_R; \frac{df2}{dc} = sk_{DV} - k_I s (\beta + (1 - \beta) a) \gamma^2 + (1 - \alpha) k_R \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{df3}{di} = 0; \frac{df3}{ds} = k_I (a + \beta c) \gamma; \frac{df3}{da} = k_I s \gamma - (k_B + k_R + k_P - ck_{DV}); \frac{df3}{dc} = k_I s (\beta + (1 - \beta) a) \gamma^2 + ak_{DV} \quad (38)$$

$$\frac{df4}{di} = \frac{df4}{ds} = 0; \frac{df4}{da} = k_P; \frac{df4}{dc} = 2ck_{DV} - (k_B + k_R + k_{DV}) \quad (39)$$

The Jacobian matrix is:

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{df1}{di} & \frac{df1}{ds} & \frac{df1}{da} & \frac{df1}{dc} \\ \frac{df2}{di} & \frac{df2}{ds} & \frac{df2}{da} & \frac{df2}{dc} \\ \frac{df3}{di} & \frac{df3}{ds} & \frac{df3}{da} & \frac{df3}{dc} \\ \frac{df4}{di} & \frac{df4}{ds} & \frac{df4}{da} & \frac{df4}{dc} \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

When evaluated at the critical point ($x = x^*$), if the real part of all eigenvalues are less than zero, the solution is locally stable. Considering the alternative system of equations shown in Appendix A with $\alpha \equiv 1$ and $k_L = (1 - \alpha) k_R (a + c) / i$:

$$\frac{df1}{di} = ck_{DV} - k_B - k_L; \frac{df1}{ds} = 0; \frac{df1}{da} = \frac{df1}{dc} = k_R \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{df2}{di} = k_L; \frac{df2}{ds} = -k_B + ck_{DV} - k_I (a + \beta c) \gamma; \frac{df2}{da} = -k_I s \gamma; \frac{df2}{dc} = sk_{DV} - k_I s (\beta + (1 - \beta) a) \gamma^2 \quad (42)$$

The expressions for $f3$ and $f4$ are unchanged.